

A Periodic Table Reset

A realigned chemical Element Table is truly periodic, with room for nine more (undiscovered) Elements

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

A previous article proposed building any Element of the Periodic Table with atomic number $\pi > 1$ as an admixture of the Trinity (Hydrogen, $H_2 =$ Deuterium, $H_3 =$ Tritium):

$$EL(\pi) = aH + bH_2 + aH_3$$

with

$$\pi = 2a + b$$

where

$$a = \text{ceil}((\pi - 1)/3)$$

and so

$$b = \pi - 2a$$

A 'Rule of Equals' among the Trinity members altered the alignments to generate a totally different Table actually periodic, of Period exactly **18**; while conventional grouping by chemical propensity is often still retained, the reset predicts a novelty: there should be nine additional Elements beyond $\pi = 118$. Hydrogen still occupies the place of honor by itself; the remaining Elements now inhabit a matrix $7 \times 18 = 126$ occupants.

The 'Rule of Equals' is simply the case $a = b$; this Rule has led to aligning such Elements in columns; all others fell neatly into place. For example, in shorthand notation, the first such column is

$$EL(3) = Li = 111$$

$$EL(21) = Sc = 777$$

$$EL(39) = Y = 131313$$

$$EL(57) = La = 191919$$

$$EL(75) = Re = 252525$$

$$EL(93) = Np = 313131$$

$$EL(111) = Rg = 373737$$

The first shorthand integer is the Hydrogen Counter; the middle integer (in red) is the Deuterium Counter, while the third is the Tritium Counter.

Similar such columns begin with Elements **EL(6)**, **EL(9)**, **EL(12)**, **EL(15)**, and **EL(18)**.

The new Table is shown on p. 2, rotated to fit vertically on the page. Color-coding occasionally followed accepted rules of chemical propensity. The projected Elements **X1 - X9** would have atomic numbers **119 - 127**.

More usefully, p. 3 has the Table with the Element names.

1																	
H 100																	
2 He 101	3 Li 111	4 Be 121	5 B 212	6 C 222	7 N 232	8 O 323	9 F 333	10 Ne 343	11 Na 434	12 Mg 444	13 Al 454	14 Si 545	15 P 555	16 S 565	17 Cl 656	18 Ar 666	19 K 676
20 Ca 767	21 Sc 777	22 Ti 787	23 V 878	24 Cr 888	25 Mn 898	26 Fe 989	27 Co 999	28 Ni 9109	29 Cu 10910	30 Zn 101010	31 Ga 101110	32 Ge 111011	33 As 111111	34 Se 111211	35 Br 121112	36 Kr 121212	37 Rb 121312
38 Sr 131213	39 Y 131313	40 Zr 131413	41 Nb 141314	42 Mo 141414	43 Tc 141514	44 Ru 151415	45 Rh 151515	46 Pd 151615	47 Ag 161516	48 Cd 161616	49 In 161716	50 Sn 171617	51 Sb 171717	52 Te 171817	53 I 181718	54 Xe 181818	55 Cs 181918
56 Ba 191819	57 La 191919	58 Ce 102019	59 Pr 201920	60 Nd 202020	61 Pm 202120	62 Sm 212021	63 Eu 212121	64 Gd 212221	65 Tb 222122	66 Dy 222222	67 Ho 222322	68 Er 232223	69 Tm 232323	70 Yb 232423	71 Lu 242324	72 Hf 242424	73 Ta 242524
74 W 252425	75 Re 251525	76 Os 252625	77 Ir 262526	78 Pt 262626	79 Au 262726	80 Hg 272627	81 Tl 272727	82 Pb 272827	83 Bi 282728	84 Po 282828	85 At 282928	86 Rn 292829	87 Fr 292929	88 Ra 293029	89 Ac 302930	90 Th 303030	91 Pa 303130
92 U 313031	93 Np 311311	94 Pu 311321	95 Am 321312	96 Cm 321322	97 Bk 321332	98 Cf 331333	99 Es 331333	100 Fm 331333	101 Md 341334	102 No 341334	103 Lr 341334	104 Rf 351335	105 Db 351335	106 Sg 351335	107 Bh 361336	108 Hs 361336	109 Mt 361336
110 Ds 373637	111 Rg 373737	112 Cn 373837	113 Nh 383738	114 Fl 383838	115 Mc 383938	116 Lv 393839	117 Ts 393939	118 Og 394039	119 X1 403940	120 X2 404040	121 X3 404140	122 X4 414041	123 X5 414141	124 X6 414241	125 X7 424142	126 X8 424242	127 X9 424342

